

EVAGUIDE

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ESSMA

Matchday Evacuation Survey

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Introduction

Introduction

Safety management remains one of the key aspects in stadium operations. As a stadium industry association, The European Stadium and Safety Management Association (ESSMA) strives to obtain an updated look on current matchday evacuation procedures and the challenges stadiums are facing nowadays.

ESSMA therefore recently conducted a survey concerning the implementation of matchday evacuation procedures and policies in European stadiums.

The goal of this survey was to gather more data on how clubs are currently preparing for a possible matchday evacuation and what they could do in the future to improve these procedures.

This report will present the results of this survey based on information gathered from 17 ESSMA members who participated.

Participants answered questions related to three main categories:

- Current procedures and processes
- Challenges
- Future investments

We hope you will find this report informative and that our conclusions will provide valuable insights into current matchday evacuation procedures.

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Data Sample

Data sample

- 0 – 25K 5
- 25 – 50K 5
- + 50K 7

Procedures & Processes

Procedures & processes

100% of clubs have procedures in place to deal with threats.

100% of clubs have evacuation plans.

- Dedicated emergency/safety plan for different scenarios
- Steward training
- Checklists
- Flow Charts

Ranges from 1 emergency plan for different situations to different plans for different scenarios

Evacuation plans: Type of document

Procedures & processes

Example: West Ham United's safety procedures

- Event Safety Policy
- Safety Management Structure
- Capacity Calculations (including P & S calculations)
- Stewarding Plan
- Medical Plan
- Stadium Fire Plans (including Fire Risk Assessment)
- Contingency Plans
- Generic Risk Assessment
- Ticketing Strategy
- Segregation Policy
- Segregation Area
- Medical Extraction Policy
- Transport, Travel and Traffic Management Plan (Inc. Parking)
- Event Management Plan – Liaison (Noise Management; Planning; Briefing)
- Event Management Plan – Opening, ingress and egress
- Event Management Plan – Structures, installations and components
- Event Management Plan – Spectators (Inc. Incident reporting & investigations)
- Planned, Preventative Maintenance/tests/inspections schedules and records
- Live and table – top exercises
- Review and audits
- Safeguarding Policy
- Staff Training Policy
- Stadium Drugs Policy
- Statement of Intent
- Stadium Induction Programme
- Health and Safety Policy
- Missing Persons Policy
- Operator Services Policy
- Catering Services Schedule
- Facilities Management Schedule
- Stewarding & Security Services Schedule
- Data Protection Policy
- Search & Screen Policy
- Code of Considerate Management
- Escalator Operation Policy
- Egress Management Policy
- Maglock Exit Gate Operation Policy
- Stewards Venue Guide & Stewards Handbook
- General Safety Certificate & Certificate Boundary Turnstiles, Block & Exit Gates (Pitch Mode)
- Turnstiles, Block & Exit Gates (Athletics Mode)
- Stadium Rules & Regulations
- Prohibited Items Policy
- Job Descriptions for Safety Management
- HVM Policy
- HVM Variation Policy – Waterways
- Ejection Policy – Stadium Events
- Ejection Policy – None Stadium Events
- Stadium Dynamic Lock Down Policy
- Fixture Change Policy
- Match Postponement MOU
- Special Police Services Agreement
- Lost Property Policy

Procedures & processes

Evacuation plans: Reviews and adjustments

Plans are normally reviewed once per year or when there are any changes to the stadium infrastructure.

10/15 clubs test or adjust evacuation plans once or twice per year.

Others:

Vitesse Arnhem: "Review for every match/event"

PGE Narodowy: "4 times per year"

SV Darmstadt: "not very often"

Systems

Which systems have been integrated in the stadium?

Other: livestream body cams

Which systems can be used in case of evacuation?

PA Systems & Displays: Guidance, information & Anti-panic
CCTV: assessing the situation, checking after evacuation
Security systems: Opening evacuation routes automatically
Wi-Fi: Direct messaging (Twitter: Nac Breda)
BMS: damage report & alarm

60% of clubs use a dispatching system to communicate to colleagues.
All of these clubs are satisfied with their dispatching system.

Roles

Who is responsible for creating the evacuation plan?

Who is responsible for approving the evacuation plan?

Remarks: *PGE Arena hired Fire protection specialists to create the evacuation plans.*

Excelsior Rotterdam worked with an external partner

Example: *West Ham United: Local Authorities, Police Department and SGSA helped approve the evacuation plan.*

Roles

Who is ultimately accountable for evacuation of the stadium:

Other:

Event controller
Fire department
Stewards

Roles

In case of an evacuation, what is the role of:

Policemen:	Assisting with the evacuation in the outside perimeter Dealing with major threats (acts of terrorism, shootings...)
Stewards:	Guiding people to the exits Crowd management inside the stadium Checking empty rooms Informing and guiding the public
Other safety personnel:	Provide traffic control Provide medical services Safety managers will coordinate the evacuation and communicate with the fire brigade, police department and all safety personnel

Evacuation

Stadiums with dedicated evacuation plans for special categories of fans:

Disabled Fans: Wheelchair slopes, evacuation with fire brigade, dedicates companion for each disabled fan, special elevators

Older Fans: Special care from stewards, Access to procedures of “disabled fans” in case of reduced mobility

Children: Need to be accomponied by adult at all times

Other Dedicated plan for non-safety staff (West Ham United)

Evacuation

How are spectators guided during an evacuation?

Stewards are used as the primary evacuation method → Human error

Police are mainly used outside the venue or when there is a major threat (act of terrorism)

Other: flexible signing inside the stadium (BV Vitesse)

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Challenges

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Challenges

Satisfaction rate current evacuation procedures

Average satisfaction rate:

8.06 / 10

Most common safe-related incidents

(Illegal) use of pyrotechnics remains a problem across European stadia

Bad crowd management/ crowd flow can cause evacuation routes to be blocked.

Previous evacuations

Have you ever had an evacuation in your stadium?

Clubs:

AFC Ajax
 PSV Eindhoven
 Borussia Dortmund
 PGE Narodowy
 SV Darmstadt

What are the most challenging aspects of an evacuation?

- Actually making the decision to evacuate is difficult but has to happen quickly.
- Communication to staff has to be fluent and clear.
- People have to be told very clearly what to do and where to go. They “have to be forced” otherwise they won’t listen.
- People have to be well-informed to prevent mass panic.
- Good preparation (stewards & safety manager) and collaboration (fire department, police department & local authorities) is essential.

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Future investments

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Investments

Which of the following categories are you planning to invest in in the near future?

Other: Biometric identification software (PSV)
Hostile Vehicle Mitigation barriers (West Ham United)

Future threats & Interest in Evaguide

Main threats for the future

Terrorism (in any form) and the damage that can be caused by one man is perceived as the largest threat.

Interest in EvaGuide Solution

15/16 clubs would be interested in a digital tool for evacuation procedures that gathers input from stewards and directly informs visitors